

Sum and product decompositions of the Lorentz Group for 4- and 6-dimensional representations

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Abstract

Let Λ_4 be the 4-dimensional irreducible vector representation of the Lorentz group.

- Λ_4 transforms four vectors.
- Λ_4 can be written as a tensor product of 2-dimensional left and right representations, $\Lambda_4 = W_A \otimes W_B$, this is also known as $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) = (\frac{1}{2}, 0) \otimes (0, \frac{1}{2})$ factorization.
- W_A and W_B act on 2-component left- and right-chiral Weyl spinors (massless fermion states). 4-component Dirac spinors (massive fermion states) are obtained by a direct sum of Weyl spinors with opposite chirality.
- Λ_4 can also be written as a matrix product of two matrices, $\Lambda_4 = Z_A Z_B$.
- We have shown elsewhere that Z_A and Z_B can be considered as left- and right-chiral representations acting on 4-component Weyl spinors. This spinor space is 4-dimensional, hence there are four linearly independent basis spinors. Two of them correspond to the left and two of them correspond to the right representation, i.e., the number of massless fermion states is doubled. Accordingly, it is possible to define two 8-component Dirac spinors that form a doublet.

We introduce Λ_6 : 6-dimensional irreducible vector representation of the Lorentz group.

- Λ_6 is designed for the Lorentz transformation of the 6-component electromagnetic vector $\vec{F} = (\vec{E}, \vec{B})$.
- Λ_6 should not be confused with the $(1, 0) \oplus (0, 1)$ reducible representation of Spin 1.
- Λ_6 cannot be written as a tensor product of 3-dimensional left and right representations.
- Λ_6 can be written as a matrix product of 6-dimensional left and right representations, $\Lambda_6 = L_A L_B$.
- L_A and L_B act on 6-component left- and right-helicity states $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$ and $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$. Action of L_A on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$ and action of L_B on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$ is a Lorentz transformation. But, L_A and L_B behave as an identity operator on the other representation, $L_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$ and $L_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$.
- Λ_6 can also be written as a matrix sum of 6-dimensional left and right representations, $\Lambda_6 = H_A + H_B$.
- Action of H_A on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$ and action of H_B on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$ is a Lorentz transformation. By definition, $\vec{F} = \frac{1}{2}(\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A + \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B)$, and accordingly we have $H_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = H_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = 0$.

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Overview

Tensor and matrix product factorizations of the 4-dimensional irreducible representation

Let us consider the following 4-dimensional vector representation of the Lorentz group, where $\mathbb{1}$ is the 2×2 identity and σ_i are the Pauli matrices:

$$\Lambda_4 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i) \otimes \mathbb{1} + (\theta_i - i\phi_i)\mathbb{1} \otimes (-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*} \quad (1)$$

It may not be easy to recognize but this is equivalent to real version of the Lorentz transformation $\Lambda_4^r = e^{(\theta_i J_i + \phi_i K_i)}$, J_i and K_i being the rotation and boost generators respectively. Λ_4^r can be obtained from Λ_4 by a transformation $\Lambda_4^r = U\Lambda_4 U^{-1}$. Explicit form of U will be given in the subsequent sections.

Since $-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i \otimes \mathbb{1}$ commutes with $\mathbb{1} \otimes (-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_j)^*$ for all i, j we can write Λ_4 as a matrix product:

$$\Lambda_4 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i) \otimes \mathbb{1}} e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)\mathbb{1} \otimes (-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*} = Z_A Z_B \quad (2)$$

where $Z_A = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i) \otimes \mathbb{1}}$, $Z_B = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)\mathbb{1} \otimes (-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*}$ and Λ_4 is expressed as a matrix product of two 4×4 matrices². As it was shown elsewhere, Z_A and Z_B are 4-dimensional spinor representations of the Lorentz group. If we regard Z_A as the left-chiral representation then Z_B corresponds to the right-chiral representation. These 4-dimensional spinor representations act on 4-component Weyl spinors ψ_L, φ_L and ψ_R, φ_R ³. In this 4-dimensional representation the number of Weyl spinors is doubled. It can also be shown that we can define two types of massive fermion states that are solutions to the extended Dirac equation forming a particle doublet.

We can also read Eq.(2) as

$$\Lambda_4 = (e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)} \otimes \mathbb{1})(\mathbb{1} \otimes e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*}) \quad (3)$$

or

$$\Lambda_4 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)} \otimes e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*} \quad (4)$$

In other words Λ_4 is also a tensor product of 2-dimensional representations $W_A = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)}$ and $W_B = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i)^*}$ which are elements of the group $SL(2, \mathbb{C})$ ⁴:

$$\Lambda_4 = W_A \otimes W_B \quad (5)$$

If we regard W_A as the left representation, W_B corresponds to the right representation. 2-dimensional left and right representations act on 2-component Weyl spinors ξ_L and ξ_R ⁵.

In summary, we have two types of product decomposition for the 4-dimensional vector representation of the Lorentz group: decomposition as a matrix product of 4-dimensional left-

²In general $Z_B \neq Z_A^*$, but when we transform $Z_{A,B} \rightarrow U Z_{A,B} U^{-1}$ we can let $Z_A = Z$, $Z_B = Z^*$ and $\Lambda_4^r = ZZ^*$ in the new basis.

³In the new basis, Z acts on ψ_L and φ_L , $(Z^{-1})^\dagger$ acts on ψ_R and φ_R .

⁴We can also write $\Lambda_4 = W \otimes W^*$, which is known as the irreducible representation $(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) = (\frac{1}{2}, 0) \otimes (0, \frac{1}{2})$.

⁵Actually, W acts on ξ_L and, $(W^{-1})^\dagger$ acts on ξ_R .

and right-spinor representations, $\Lambda_4 = Z_A^{4 \times 4} Z_B^{4 \times 4}$; or, as a tensor product of 2-dimensional left- and right-spinor representations $\Lambda_4 = W_A^{2 \times 2} \otimes W_B^{2 \times 2}$.

In the following we will introduce a 6-dimensional vector representation of the Lorentz group, Λ_6 , that is tailored for the transformations of the 6-component electromagnetic field vector. Obviously, a 6-dimensional irreducible representation cannot be factorized as a tensor product of 3-dimensional representations, but it will be shown that a sum decomposition of Λ_6 in terms of 6-dimensional left- and right-helical representations is possible, in addition to the matrix product decomposition.

Sum and product decompositions of the 6-dimensional irreducible vector representation

(Warning! This 6-dimensional irreducible representation should not be confused with the reducible $(1, 0) \oplus (0, 1)$ representation of spin 1)

As we have shown elsewhere, Λ_6 is a 6-dimensional irreducible vector representation of the Lorentz group that acts on the 6-component electromagnetic vector $\vec{F} = (\vec{E}, \vec{B})$:

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i + (\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i} \quad (6)$$

where e and ϵ are the elements such that $e^2 = \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$, $\epsilon^2 = -\mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$, $h = \frac{1}{2}(e - i\epsilon)$, $hh^* = 0$, $h^n = h$ and S_i are the generators of the group $\text{SO}(3)$:

$$e = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Λ_6 can equivalently be written in terms of rotation and boost generators J_i and K_i : $\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i J_i + \phi_i K_i)}$.

Since $h \otimes S_i$ commutes with $h^* \otimes S_j$ for all i, j we can write ⁶

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i} e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i} \quad (8)$$

We can regard $L_A = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i}$ and $L_B = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i}$ as left- and right-helical representations, and simply write ⁷

$$\Lambda_6 = L_A L_B \quad (9)$$

In short, Λ_6 is a matrix product of 6-dimensional representations L_A and L_B that act on 6-component left- and right-helicity states. Details can be found in the subsequent sections.

On the other hand, after some algebra, due the property $h^n = h$ Eq.(8) can also be read as

$$\Lambda_6 = (h^* \otimes \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} + h \otimes e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)S_i})(h \otimes \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} + h^* \otimes e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)S_i}) \quad (10)$$

Since $hh^* = 0$ and $h^2 = h$ this reduces to

$$\Lambda_6 = h \otimes e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)S_i} + h^* \otimes e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)S_i} \quad (11)$$

⁶Actually, we have a more stringent condition than commuting, $(h \otimes S_i)(h^* \otimes S_j) = 0$ because $hh^* = 0$.

⁷In the representation given in Eq.(7), $L_B = L_A^* = L^*$, hence $\Lambda_6 = LL^*$, but this not true in general.

If we let $H_A = h \otimes e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)S_i}$, $H_B = h^* \otimes e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)S_i}$, Λ_6 turns out to be a sum of two matrices ⁸:

$$\Lambda_6 = H_A + H_B \quad (12)$$

When we consider the action of H_A and H_B on the helicity states we observe that H_A and H_B can be regarded as left- and right-helical representations ⁹.

As a result, although the lie algebra of 4-dimensional and 6-dimensional representations are the same ¹⁰ their group structures are different. We can write Λ_4 as a matrix product of 4-dimensional, and as a tensor product of 2-dimensional left- and right-chiral representations:

$$\Lambda_4 = Z_A^{4 \times 4} Z_B^{4 \times 4} = W_A^{2 \times 2} \otimes W_B^{2 \times 2} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, we can write Λ_6 as a matrix product of 6-dimensional left- and right-helical representations; but, obviously, we cannot write Λ_6 as a tensor product of 3-dimensional representations. Instead, Λ_6 can be written as a matrix sum of two parts that can be regarded as left- and right-helical representations:

$$\Lambda_6 = L_A^{6 \times 6} L_B^{6 \times 6} = H_A^{6 \times 6} + H_B^{6 \times 6} \quad (14)$$

Actions on the states

Interpretations of L_A and H_A as left, L_B and H_B as right representations becomes clear when we consider the action of the transformations on the vectors:

Let S_A and S_B be Lorentz transformations for (1, 0) and (0, 1) representations of Spin 1. And let $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_A = \vec{E} - i\vec{B}$ and $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_B = \vec{E} + i\vec{B}$ be Riemann-Silberstein vectors, where \vec{E} and \vec{B} are electric and magnetic field vectors. S_A and S_B can act on either $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_A$ or $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_B$ to yield a Lorentz transformation ¹¹. On the other hand, L_A induces a Lorentz transformation (LT) only when it acts on the 6-dimensional vector $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_A = L_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A, \quad \text{where} \quad \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\mathcal{E}}_A \\ i\vec{\mathcal{E}}_A \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Similarly, L_B is a Lorentz transformation only when it acts on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_B = L_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B, \quad \text{where} \quad \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\mathcal{E}}_B \\ -i\vec{\mathcal{E}}_B \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

L_A and L_B behave as an identity on the other representation, $L_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$, $L_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$.

As we come to the 6-dimensional representation, the action of H_A on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$ and the action of H_B on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$ results in a Lorentz transformation, but $H_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = 0$ and $H_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = 0$. These properties are consistent with the relations $\Lambda_6 = H_A + H_B$ and $\vec{F} = \frac{1}{2}(\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A + \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B)$.

⁸Notice that $H_A H_B = 0$, because $h h^* = 0$.

⁹In the representation given in Eq. (7) $H_B = H_A^*$, hence we can let $H_A = H$ and $H_B = H^*$, then $\Lambda_6 = H + H^*$.

¹⁰See the supplementary materials

¹¹In case of boosts, the sign of the boost direction is reversed when S_A acts on $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_B$, but the result is still a Lorentz transformation. Same deal for S_B on $\vec{\mathcal{E}}_A$.

Supplementary material 1

1. Four-dimensional representations of the Lorentz group

Let us begin with the well known real vector representation of the Lorentz group:

$$\Lambda_4^r = e^{(\theta_i J_i + \phi_i K_i)} \quad (17)$$

where we use all real representation of the generators J_i and K_i :

$$J_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad J_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad J_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$K_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad K_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad K_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

We have the following commutation relations:

$$[J_i, J_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [K_i, K_j] = -\epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [J_i, K_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} K_k \quad (20)$$

We follow the standard procedure and define:

$$M_i^r = \frac{1}{2}(J_i - iK_i), \quad N_i^r = \frac{1}{2}(J_i + iK_i) \quad (21)$$

Now we change the basis:

$$M_i = U^{-1} M_i^r U, \quad N_i = U^{-1} N_i^r U \quad (22)$$

where

$$U = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad U^{-1} = U^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

After applying the transformations we get:

$$M_i = \left(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i\right) \otimes \mathbb{1}, \quad N_i = \mathbb{1} \otimes \left(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i\right)^* \quad (24)$$

In the new basis the Lorentz transformation matrix reads

$$\Lambda_4 = e^{(\theta+i\phi)\left(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i\right) \otimes \mathbb{1} + (\theta-i\phi)\mathbb{1} \otimes \left(-\frac{i}{2}\sigma_i\right)^*} \quad (25)$$

In this somewhat disguised form Λ_4 acts on the complex 4-vector V

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} t + z \\ x - iy \\ x + iy \\ t - z \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

After transforming back we recover the familiar 4×4 real representation:

$$\Lambda_4^r = U \Lambda_4 U^{-1} \quad (27)$$

Λ_4^r acts on the real vector V^r

$$V^r = \begin{pmatrix} t \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (28)$$

2. Four-component Weyl spinors and doubling the number of massless fermions

Let us define $\Sigma_i = U(\sigma_i \otimes \mathbb{1})U^{-1}$. Then we can write 4×4 version of $\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ in terms of Σ_i :

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & n_1 & n_2 & n_3 \\ n_1 & 0 & -in_3 & in_2 \\ n_2 & in_3 & 0 & -in_1 \\ n_3 & -in_2 & in_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = (\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \Sigma_3)$ and $\mathbf{n} = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$. $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is a traceless Hermitian matrix and it has four orthogonal eigenvectors for $u = \cos(\theta/2)$, $v = \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi}$:

$$\psi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ -iv \\ u \end{pmatrix}, \quad \psi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v^* \\ -u^* \\ iu^* \\ v^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} v \\ u \\ iu \\ -v \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -u^* \\ v^* \\ iv^* \\ u^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

ψ_L and φ_L correspond to $+1$ and ψ_R and φ_R correspond to -1 eigenvalue. Actually, these are 4-component Weyl spinors, and they are the solutions to the following version of the Weyl equations:

$$\left(i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}\right) \xi = 0 \quad (31)$$

$$\left(i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p}\right) \chi = 0 \quad (32)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = |\mathbf{p}|\mathbf{n}$. Plane wave ansatz for positive and negative energies suggest that ψ_L and φ_L are left-chiral, ψ_R and φ_R are right-chiral, particle/antiparticle solutions. Therefore, in the 4-dimensional representation the number of massless fermions is doubled.

$\psi_L, \psi_R, \varphi_L$ and φ_R constitute a basis for 4-dimensional vector space. Left- and right-chiral spinors are related to each other by the spinor metric g :

$$\psi_R = (g\psi_L)^*, \quad \varphi_R = (g\varphi_L)^* \quad (33)$$

where ¹²

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad g^{-1} = g^\dagger \quad (34)$$

Left- and right-chiral spinors transform as

$$\psi_L \rightarrow \psi'_L = Z\psi_L, \quad \varphi_L \rightarrow \varphi'_L = Z\varphi_L \quad (35)$$

$$\psi_R \rightarrow \psi'_R = (Z^{-1})^\dagger \psi_R, \quad \varphi_R \rightarrow \varphi'_R = (Z^{-1})^\dagger \varphi_R \quad (36)$$

Z and $(Z^{-1})^\dagger$ are expressed in Σ_i basis and they correspond to 4×4 versions of the left and right $\text{SL}(2, \mathbb{C})$ representations. Z preserves both the spinor metric g and the Minkowski metric η ¹³.

$$Z^T g Z = g, \quad Z^T \eta Z = \eta \quad (37)$$

¹² 2×2 spinor matrix is given by $\epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. It may be suggested that 4×4 version of ϵ can be obtained as $U(\epsilon \otimes \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2})U^{-1}$. But this gives $i\Sigma_2$ which is not true. In fact, $g = i\eta\Sigma_2^*$ and it explicitly involves the Minkowski metric η .

¹³Also, $(Z^{-1})^\dagger$ preserves g and η .

Since η is real, $Z^T \eta Z = \eta$ directly entails $\Lambda^T \eta \Lambda = \eta$. In an analogy with $\epsilon \sigma_i \epsilon^{-1} = -\sigma_i^*$, we have the following very useful relation:

$$g \Sigma_i g^{-1} = -\Sigma_i^* \quad (38)$$

Supplementary material 2

Six-dimensional representations of the Lorentz group

1. Extension and complexification of the group SO(3)

Let \vec{F} be a six component electromagnetic vector:

$$\vec{F} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{E} \\ \vec{B} \end{pmatrix} \quad (39)$$

And let Λ_6 be a 6×6 Lorentz transformation matrix acting on \vec{F} that can be written in terms of parameters θ_i and ϕ_i and rotation and boost generators J_i and K_i :

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i J_i + \phi_i K_i)} \quad (40)$$

where

$$J_1 = e \otimes S_1, \quad J_2 = e \otimes S_2, \quad J_3 = e \otimes S_3 \quad (41)$$

$$K_1 = \epsilon \otimes S_1, \quad K_2 = \epsilon \otimes S_2, \quad K_3 = \epsilon \otimes S_3 \quad (42)$$

S_1, S_2, S_3 are the generators of the SO(3) group and e and ϵ are the extension units with the properties, $e^2 = \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$, $\epsilon^2 = -\mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2}$:

$$e = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

In this irreducible representation ϵ plays the role of the imaginary unit and serves for the complexification of the algebra.

We have the following commutation relations:

$$[J_i, J_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [K_i, K_j] = -\epsilon_{ijk} J_k, \quad [J_i, K_j] = \epsilon_{ijk} K_k \quad (44)$$

This is the algebra of SO(1,3).

Under the rotations electric and magnetic field vectors rotate independently. Boosts are more interesting. Explicit form of a boost in an arbitrary direction and its action on \vec{F} reads

$$\begin{pmatrix} E'_x \\ E'_y \\ E'_z \\ B'_x \\ B'_y \\ B'_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma + \frac{\beta_x^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x \beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x \beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & 0 & -\beta_z \gamma & \beta_y \gamma \\ \frac{\beta_y \beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_y^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_y \beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \beta_z \gamma & 0 & -\beta_x \gamma \\ \frac{\beta_z \beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_z \beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_z^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & -\beta_y \gamma & \beta_x \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_z \gamma & -\beta_y \gamma & \gamma + \frac{\beta_x^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x \beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_x \beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \\ -\beta_z \gamma & 0 & \beta_x \gamma & \frac{\beta_y \beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_y^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_y \beta_z(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \\ \beta_y \gamma & -\beta_x \gamma & 0 & \frac{\beta_z \beta_x(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \frac{\beta_z \beta_y(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} & \gamma + \frac{\beta_z^2(1-\gamma)}{\beta^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \\ E_z \\ B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (45)$$

The irreducible representation Λ_6 preserves a metric g_6 which plays the role of the Minkowski metric:

$$\Lambda_6^T g_6 \Lambda_6 = g_6, \quad \text{where,} \quad g_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (46)$$

With this metric we can define the scalar product and obtain one of the Lorentz invariants of the electromagnetic field:

$$\vec{F} \cdot \vec{F} = \vec{F}^T g_6 \vec{F} = |\vec{E}|^2 - |\vec{B}|^2 \quad (47)$$

2. Left- and right-helical representations

Let us define new generators:

$$M_i = \frac{1}{2}(J_i - iK_i) = \frac{1}{2}(e \otimes S_i - i\epsilon \otimes S_i) = h \otimes S_i, \quad N_i = \frac{1}{2}(J_i + iK_i) = \frac{1}{2}(e \otimes S_i + i\epsilon \otimes S_i) = h^* \otimes S_i \quad (48)$$

M_i and N_i obey the SU(2) algebra and commute with each other. We rewrite Λ_6 in terms of M_i and N_i or equivalently in terms of $h \otimes S_i$ and $h^* \otimes S_i$:

$$\Lambda_6 = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i + (\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i} \quad (49)$$

Let us denote $L_A = e^{(\theta_i + i\phi_i)h \otimes S_i}$ and $L_B = e^{(\theta_i - i\phi_i)h^* \otimes S_i}$. Since $[M_i, N_j] = 0$, Λ_6 can be written as matrix product, $\Lambda_6 = L_A L_B$, where L_A and L_B can be regarded as 6-dimensional left- and right-helical irreducible representations¹⁴.

We can define 6-dimensional versions of Eqs.(29)-(32), i.e., 6-dimensional versions of $\sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ and Weyl equations. Left- and right-helical representations act on the solutions to these equations that are 6-component complex vectors. For example, L_A acts on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\mathcal{E}} \\ i\vec{\mathcal{E}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{where} \quad \vec{\mathcal{E}} = \vec{E} - i\vec{B} \quad (50)$$

The metric g_6 that given in Eq.(46) is also preserved by L_A and L_B :

$$L_A^T g_6 L_A = g_6, \quad L_B^T g_6 L_B = g_6 \quad (51)$$

Hence we can define the scalar product and find the associated Lorentz invariants:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A \cdot \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A^T g_6 \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = |\vec{E}|^2 - |\vec{B}|^2 - 2i\vec{E} \cdot \vec{B} \quad (52)$$

¹⁴In this representation $L_B = L_A^*$, but this is not true in general.

3. Compact forms

We can write explicit forms of L_A, L_B, H_A and H_B in a very handy condensed notation by means of a 3×3 matrix T :

$$L_A = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} + T/2 & -iT/2 \\ iT/2 & \mathbb{1} + T/2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad L_B = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} + T^*/2 & iT^*/2 \\ -iT^*/2 & \mathbb{1} + T^*/2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (53)$$

$$H_A = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} + T & -i(\mathbb{1} + T) \\ i(\mathbb{1} + T) & \mathbb{1} + T \end{pmatrix}, \quad H_B = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} + T^* & i(\mathbb{1} + T^*) \\ -i(\mathbb{1} + T^*) & \mathbb{1} + T^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (54)$$

Here we use the property that in the given basis $L_B = L_A^*$ and $H_B = H_A^*$.

$\mathbb{1} + T$ gives the $(0, 1)$ representation of Spin 1. Explicit forms of T for pure rotations and boosts are as follows:

$$T_{Rotation} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\theta_z^2 + \theta_y^2}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) & \frac{\theta_x \theta_y}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) - \frac{\theta_z}{\theta} \sin \theta & \frac{\theta_x \theta_z}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) + \frac{\theta_y}{\theta} \sin \theta \\ \frac{\theta_y \theta_x}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) + \frac{\theta_z}{\theta} \sin \theta & -\frac{\theta_z^2 + \theta_x^2}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) & \frac{\theta_y \theta_z}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) - \frac{\theta_x}{\theta} \sin \theta \\ \frac{\theta_z \theta_x}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) - \frac{\theta_y}{\theta} \sin \theta & \frac{\theta_z \theta_y}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) + \frac{\theta_x}{\theta} \sin \theta & -\frac{\theta_x^2 + \theta_y^2}{\theta^2}(1 - \cos \theta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (55)$$

$$T_{Boost} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\phi_z^2 + \phi_y^2}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) & \frac{\phi_x \phi_y}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) - i\frac{\phi_z}{\phi} \sin \phi & \frac{\phi_x \phi_z}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) + i\frac{\phi_y}{\phi} \sin \phi \\ \frac{\phi_y \phi_x}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) + i\frac{\phi_z}{\phi} \sin \phi & -\frac{\phi_z^2 + \phi_x^2}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) & \frac{\phi_y \phi_z}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) - i\frac{\phi_x}{\phi} \sin \phi \\ \frac{\phi_z \phi_x}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) - i\frac{\phi_y}{\phi} \sin \phi & \frac{\phi_z \phi_y}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) + i\frac{\phi_x}{\phi} \sin \phi & -\frac{\phi_x^2 + \phi_y^2}{\phi^2}(1 - \cos \phi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (56)$$

where $\theta = \sqrt{\theta_x^2 + \theta_y^2 + \theta_z^2}$ and $\phi = \sqrt{\phi_x^2 + \phi_y^2 + \phi_z^2}$. By means of these compact forms we can easily show that

$$\Lambda_6 = L_A L_B = H_A + H_B = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{1} + \text{Re}(T) & +\text{Im}(T) \\ -\text{Im}(T) & \mathbb{1} + \text{Re}(T) \end{pmatrix} \quad (57)$$

And it is easy to show that L_A and H_A are left representations that perform Lorentz transformation on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A$ and L_B and H_B are right representations acting on $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_B$:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_A = L_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A, \quad \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_B = L_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B \quad (58)$$

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_A \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_A = H_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A, \quad \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B \xrightarrow{\text{LT}} \vec{\mathcal{F}}'_B = H_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B \quad (59)$$

We also have the following properties when left and right representation act on the other kind:

$$L_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B, \quad L_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A, \quad (60)$$

$$H_A \vec{\mathcal{F}}_B = 0, \quad H_B \vec{\mathcal{F}}_A = 0 \quad (61)$$